

Investigating the relationship between epidemiological and clinical parameters in asymptomatic obese subjects: A gender-based study

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Obesity, is a complex health condition that poses mild health issues in the initially and increases the risk of chronic illness later. **Objectives:** Identify potential early risk indicators based on gender-specific differences that contribute to future development of chronic illness in asymptomatic obese. **Methods:** Epidemiological and clinical parameters were recorded of 90 subjects at OPD, Department of Medicine, KGMU, Lucknow. Chi-square test and t-test was done to analyse data. **Results:** Significant relation was seen among different variables and obesity in both genders (marital status: males, $p=0.00$; females, $p=0.00$, educational level: males, $p=0.046$; females, $p=0.000$, family type: males, $p=0.033$; females, $p=0.001$, occupation: males, $p=0.001$; females, $p=0.00$). Systolic blood pressure (SBP, $p = 0.001$) was significantly higher among men, whereas Waist-to-height ratio (WHtR, $p = 0.05$) slightly higher in females. **Conclusions:** Strong relation between obesity and epidemiological, clinical parameters indicates poor lifestyle and long-term health risk in symptomatic obese. Males were at risk of HTN (Higher SBP). Whereas, abdominal obesity in females indicates risk of heart relates future issues. The findings underscore the need for early lifestyle interventions to mitigate long-term health risks in this population.

Keywords: Obesity, BMI, asymptomatic, WHtR, Gender.

INTRODUCTION:

Obesity is a heterogeneous condition related with different types of co-morbidities such as T2DM, Cardiovascular diseases, dyslipidemia, and thyroid imbalance. For the development of effective preventive and therapeutic strategies, understanding of gender-specific patterns and related co-morbidities of obesity is very crucial. According to a Portuguese study, about 66.6% male and 57.9% female were under BMI>25 kg/m². Obesity was seen more prevalent among less educated population. Decrease education level acts as risk factor for obesity in the population [1]. Prevalence of obesity was higher in women than men (22.5% and 10.5% respectively). Obesity was a usual problem in Iran nowadays. Obesity was seen more prevalent in the women population instead of men. In Iranian adults, intake of junk food and low physical activity due to speedy modernization, urbanization could be a reason to the increased BMI [2].

Prevalence of obesity was high in female population as compare to the male. Urbanization, increasing education and income level were seen as crucial risk factor for obesity [3].

Both types of obesity, generalised and central were commonly found among female individuals than male individuals. Waist-Hip ratio was increased among females (64.6%) than males (31.3%). Obesity or central obesity rate was low among highly educated individuals, which was contrary to some studies. The odds of occurring diabetes, hypercholesteremia (high amount of cholesterol in the blood) and hypertension increases with the incident of obesity or central obesity [4]. Among adults of Uganda, in the prevalence of obesity, remarkable gender difference was observed but in prevalence of overweight between rural-urban population, any difference was not noticed. Female were more obese (2.9% vs. 1.8%) and overweight (17.4% vs. 3.3%) as compared to the males. Major risk

factors were urbanization, smoking, consumption of alcohol, less physical activity and increasing richness of family. Females, who were less active and not engaged in any physical activity or sports, were at risk being overweight [5].

In contrast to some studies, men were seen more prone to the generalised obesity as well as for central obesity than the women and with age, obesity and overweight increases and then decreases, whereas central obesity consistently increases. In females, BMI and abdominal obesity was higher than the males (37% versus 13.3%) and 94.2.6% versus 15.6%) respectively. Variation was seen in the incident of obesity according to the gender. Women were fatter than men in urban area but according to the education status highly educated subjects were less obese [6]. In the case of obesity prevalence, considerable diversity was seen among women than men. Sex differences were highly correlated to the incident of obesity [7].

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Study Design and Settings:

It is a hospital based cross-sectional study implemented in the Out-Patient Department (OPD) of Department of Medicine, King George’s Medical University, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India. After taking ethical approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee and consent from the subjects, 90 asymptomatic subjects of both genders were included. Subjects, aged 18-60 years with mild health issues or no issues were included. Individuals with any chronic disease, pregnant or lactating women were excluded from the study.

Anthropometric Measures:

To collect demographic information, medical issues, and lifestyle factors questionnaire was used. The questionnaire included anthropometric measurements (Weight, Height, BMI, Waist circumference (WC), Hip Circumference (HC), Waist-Hip ratio (WHR), Waist-Height ratio (WHtR)), Body mass index (BMI) was calculated with the Quetelet Index; $BMI (kg/m^2) = \text{weight (kg)} / \text{height}^2 (m^2)$ and hip circumference, waist circumference was measured with the help of measuring tape. Obese subjects were classified on the basis of

WHO classification for Asian Indian population (Obesity, $BMI > 25$).

Clinical Measures:

Clinical parameters, Blood Pressure (BP), Random Blood Sugar (RBS) level, Glycated Haemoglobin (HbA1C) were recorded. Blood pressure was recorded in the resting position and non-fasting blood glucose level was measured by random blood sugar (RBS) test and glycated haemoglobin test (HbA1C) was used to estimate past 2-3 month’s blood sugar level.

Statistical Analysis:

Mean value of BMI, WC, HC, WHtR, WHR, RBS, and HbA1C calculated for the both genders. Chi-square test was performed to analyse the relationship of the variables such as educational status, family type, economic status, occupation eating habits, and lifestyle. Furthermore, independent student t-test was applied to compare variables of females and males, working and non-working women. All the statistical analysis was done by SPSS (version-20).

RESULTS:

In present study, about 52.2% were female and 47.7% were male population. About 56% males and 44% females falls in class-I obesity ($BMI = 25-29.9 kg/m^2$) and 37.5% males and 62.5% females fall in class-II obesity ($BMI = 30-45 kg/m^2$).

In the study population, mean value of height in females was 154.7 cm and 166.6 cm in males. Males (81.6 kg) had higher mean value of weight than female (72.13 kg). Both males and females had abdominal obesity but mean value of waist circumference and hip circumference was slightly higher in females (WC-Females= 101.8 cm, Males 100.2 cm; HC-Females=101.68 cm, Males= 100.3 cm). Females (WHR mean= 2.25) were centrally obese as compared to the males (WHR mean=1.005). Generalised obesity was also higher in women ($BMI = 30.9 kg/m^2$) than men ($BMI = 29.4 kg/m^2$). Both genders were non-diabetic, their glycated haemoglobin test (HbA1C) and random blood sugar was in normal range (RBS) (Table 1).

Table 1: Showing mean value of different anthropometric and biological parameters of both genders of the study.

Parameters	Females (Mean)	Males (Mean)
Height (cm)	154.7	166.6
Weight (kg)	72.13	81.6
Hip Circumference (cm)	101.68	100.3
Waist Circumference (cm)	101.8	100.2
WHtR	0.65	0.60
BMI (kg/m^2)	30.9	29.4
WHR	2.25	1.005
RBS (mg/dl)	113.40	129.2
HbA1C	5.2	5.5

WHR=waist-hip ratio, WHtR=waist-height ratio, BMI= body mass index, RBS= random blood sugar, HbA1C= glycated haemoglobin

Association between demographic variables and males were analysed by using Chi-square test and it was seen that in males, marital status, educational status, and family structure (nuclear or joint) all shows significant relationship with obesity. The analysis exhibit that marital status ($\chi^2= 25.324, p = 0.000$), educational status ($\chi^2= 25.319, p = 0.046$), and family status ($\chi^2 = 8.759, p = 0.033$) all were significantly linked to obesity (**Table 2**).

In males, occupation was significantly related with obesity ($\chi^2= 34.181, p = 0.001$). However, economic status ($\chi^2= 4.953, p = 0.838$), eating habits ($\chi^2= 3.061, p = 0.382$), and lifestyle ($\chi^2= 6.612, p = 0.358$) do not showed significant relationship with obesity (**Table 2**). Association between female variables and obesity were also analysed by using Chi-Square test, and it was seen that educational status, marital status, and family structure (nuclear or joint) were significantly related with obesity. Married women were obese as compare to

the other women ($\chi^2= 31.458, p = 0.000$). Positive relation was seen between obesity and educational level and this association was more prevalent among undergraduates' females (44.4%) of 20-29 age group ($\chi^2= 48.693, p = 0.000$). In nuclear families 77.8% obese in 20-29 age group and individuals of joint families, was more obese and obesity prevalence was higher in the age group of 40-49 ($\chi^2= 22.698, p = 0.001$). Young females of nuclear families were more obese than joint. In contrast, type of residence, like urban and rural, was insignificantly related with obesity in females ($\chi^2= 1.223, p = 0.748$) (**Table 2**).

Whereas, occupation was strongly associated with obese females ($\chi^2= 33.976, p = 0.00$). However, relationship of economic status ($\chi^2= 11.761, p = 0.068$), eating habits ($\chi^2= 0.811, p = 0.847$), and lifestyle ($\chi^2= 8.784, p = 0.186$) was statistically insignificant with obesity (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Showing different parameters of demographic (marital status, education status, occupation, economic status, family type, eating habit, and lifestyle) and their relation with age groups of males and females.

Variables		Males Age Groups				Chi-Square	p-value	Female Age Groups				Chi-Square	p-value
		20-29 (n= %)	30-39 (n= %)	40-49 (n= %)	50-69 (n= %)			20-29 (n= %)	30-39 (n= %)	40-49 (n= %)	50-69 (n= %)		
Marital Status	Married	25	90.9	100	100	25.3	0.000	11.1	85.7	100.0	100.0	31.458	0.000*
	Unmarried	75.0	9.1	0	0			88.9	14.3	0	0		
	Widower	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0		
	Divorced	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0		
Education Status	Illiterate	0	9.1	7.7	54.5	25.3	0.046*	0	0	16.7	75	48.693	0.000*
	Primary	0	9.1	15.4	9.1			0	0	25	16.7		
	10	12.5	18.2	15.4	0			0	7.1	25	0		
	12	12.5	9.1	46.2	18.2			33.3	35.7	8.3	0		
	UG	50	36.4	7.7	18.2			44.4	28.6	16.7	8.3		
	PG	25	18.2	7.7	0			22.2	28.6	0	0		
	Profession all	0	0	0	0			0	0	8.3	0		
Family Type	Nuclear	75	36.4	46.2	9.1	8.759	0.033*	77.8	50	8.3	0	22.698	0.001*
	Joint	25	63.6	53.8	90.9			22.2	42.9	91.7	83.3		
Occupation	Not working	0	0	7.7	0	34.181	0.001*	0	64.3	91.7	83.3	33.976	0.001*
	Student	62.5	9.1	0	0			77.8	7.1	8.3	8.3		
	Private	25.0	54.5	46.2	0			22.2	28.6	0	0		
	Government	0	9.1	23.1	36.4			0	0	0	0		
	Farmer	12.5	27.3	23.1	63.6			0	0	0	8.3		
Economic status	BPL	12.5	27.3	23.1	63.6	4.953	0.838	0	14.3	50	50	11.761	0.068
	Lower	50	27.3	23.1	18.2			22.2	35.7	16.7	25		
	Lower middle	37.5	45.5	38.5	36.4			77.8	50	33.3	25		
	Upper middle	0	0	7.7	18.2			0	0	0	0		
	Vegetarian	75	63.6	38.5	54.5			3.061	0.382	66.7	50		

Eating habit	Non-vegetarian	25	36.4	61.5	45.5			33.3	50	50	41.7		
Lifestyle	Sedentary	12.5	9.1	7.7	36.4	6.612	0.358	11.1	35.7	8.3	8.3	8.784	0.186
	Moderate	62.5	36.4	38.5	27.3			22.2	35.7	58.3	58.3		
	Active	25	54.5	53.8	36.4			66.7	28.6	33.3	33.3		

* p value<0.05, UG= under graduate, PG= post graduate, BPL= below the poverty line

Student t-test was performed to compare gender, after analysis only waist to height ratio (WHtR, p=0.05) was found related with obesity significantly, showing central obesity. Which is crucial risk factor for diseases such as cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome etc. Systolic blood pressure (p=0.001) of both genders was related significantly but no significant association was seen in between diastolic blood pressure (p=0.071) of males and females (Table 3). Waist to hip ratio used to depicts central obesity and related risk. Hence, we can say that both genders could be more prone to the cardio-metabolic risk and other health issues related to central

obesity. In the comparison of working and non-working women, education status (p=0.01) and economic status (p=0.01) were significantly related (Table 3). Systolic BP was significantly higher in non-working women (p = 0.026), possibly reflecting a more sedentary lifestyle or stress-related factors. Working women were economically strong and well educated than non-working women, and status of economic condition and strong relation was seen between education level and obesity (p = 0.01 for both), highlighting socioeconomic disparities that may influence health behaviours and access to healthcare (Table 3).

Table 3: Represents Comparison between Male and Female, Working Women and Non-working Subjects

variables	Males	Females	t-test	p-value	Working Women	Non-Working Women	t-test	p-value
BP (Systolic)	133.7 ± 20.5	120.2 ± 18.5	3.283	0.001*	112.35±15.61	124.73±18.77	2.303	0.026*
BP (Diastolic)	89.5 ± 10.6	85.1 ± 12.1	1.819	0.072	85.59±17.27	84.87±8.41	-0.193	0.848
Pulse	93.0± 11.96	98.13± 19.58	-1.48	0.14	97.47±11.58	98.50±23.10	0.171	0.87
WHtR	0.60±0.06	0.66±0.06	-4.10	0.05*	0.66±0.05	0.65±0.07	-0.369	0.71
RBS (mg/dl)	128.60±56.19	113.96±28.77	1.576	0.12	117.82±38.65	111.77±21.79	-0.69	0.49
HbA1C	5.52± 1.17	5.29± 0.79	1.109	0.27	5.42±0.82	25.16±109.52	0.739	0.46
Eating habit	1.44± 0.50	1.45± 0.50	-0.047	0.963	1.41±0.51	1.47±0.51	0.356	0.72
Economic status	2.33±0.89	2.15± 0.86	0.956	0.341	2.59±0.71	1.90±0.84	-2.833	0.01*
Education status	3.63± 1.68	3.55± 1.85	0.2	0.842	4.53±1.55	3.00±1.80	-2.939	0.01*
Residency	1.47± 0.50	1.62± 0.49	-1.446	0.152	1.59±0.51	1.63±0.49	0.299	0.77

* p value<0.05, BP= blood pressure, WHtR= waist-height ratio, RBS= random blood sugar, HbA1C= glycated haemoglobin.

DISCUSSION:

Obesity is a major growing health issue nowadays due to changing lifestyle and dietary habits. In Indian population, abdominal obesity was prevalent. Increased age, increased educational level, marital status, urbanization, being female, high wealth index were the factors, which influence the both abdominal and generalised obesity [8]. Obese male (56%) was higher into the BMI 25-29.5 than female (44%) but this association was reversed for the BMI 30-45 (Male= 37.5%, Female= 62.5%). As per studies of the Indian NFHS and other study, obesity increases with age in male and female [9,10]. According to Shabu S. A. et al., females, low educated peoples, less active, unemployed and married population had greater chance of being obese and overweight [11].

Furthermore, in some studies, women living in nuclear family (about 77.8 % in 20-29 age groups) were at risk

of obesity than people living in joint family. Consumption of junk food and western culture could be a reason for this difference. Prevalence of obesity was higher in lower middle-class family. In housewives, higher level of BMI was seen in Syrian women and central obesity, generalise obesity were positively related with [12]. It was seen that house wives and lower socioeconomic status increases the risk of obesity [13]. According to Gridhar S. Et al., obesity elevates risk of hypertension in obese women. Rate of obesity was higher among housewives of middle age and middle class or higher economic class [14]. Women from wealthy house and highly educated were more susceptible for overweight or obese in Bangladesh. Unemployment was also a risk factor for being obese or overweight [15,16].

In the study, marital status (Males- $\chi^2=25.5$, p=0.00; Females- $\chi^2= 31.458$, p=0.00) educational level (Males- $\chi^2=25.5$, p=0.046; $\chi^2=48.693$, p=0.00), family status

(Males- $\chi^2=8.759$, $p=0.033$; Females- $\chi^2= 22.698$, $p=0.001$), and occupation ($\chi^2=34.181$, $p=0.001$) tend to significantly related with obesity in males and females. Women from wealthy house and highly educated were more susceptible to overweight or obese in Bangladesh. Unemployment was also a risk factor for being obese or overweight [15]. Socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, occupation, marital status, and residential area had high influence on BMI and therefore they altogether increase the risk of being overweight or obese. Female seems to be more prone of being obese compare to the male [16]. In a study, female gender was seen positively related with obesity [10, 17, 18]. The highest waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) was observed among women (both urban and rural) in Jammu and Kashmir, followed by Ladakh. These results highlight the growing prevalence of overweight/obesity and central obesity in both men and women across urban and rural regions of India. Policymakers must address this escalating issue promptly to alleviate the burden on the healthcare system[9].

In the present study, waist to height ratio of male and female ($t= -4.10$, $p=0.05$) was statistically significant but mean value of female WHtR (Mean=0.66) was greater than male (Mean=0.60). Waist circumference and waist-hip ratio was analysed to know the prevalence of central obesity. Central obesity prevalence was 53% and 33% in Syrian women as determined by WC and WHR respectively. In married individuals, low educated, physically non-active and house wives, body mass index and other anthropometric factors were positively related. For defining central obesity WC and WHR are more appropriate than the body mass index; Whereas, BMI could be used to assess generalised obesity [8].

Significant impact on women as compared to men warrants gender sensitive strategies [19]. However, according to a study, overall obesity was clustered in certain regions of United State, the patterns of gender inequality in obesity were distinct and also exhibit spatial clustering. Occupation and physical inactivity were involved in the etiology of the gender inequality of obesity prevalence [20]. In present study, individuals were abiding from mild health problem but they don't have any chronic illness or co-morbidities. Whereas, other subjects had some mild issues related with sleep and other weight (obesity) related health issues like joint- back pain, feet pain difficulty in doing any kind of physical activity. They also had breathlessness problem during physical work and some subjects were also suffering from the problem of swelling in the body. Despite these entire health problems, initially they don't show any chronic illness like heart related problem, thyroid, diabetes, or any other disease.

CONCLUSION:

Our findings indicates that among obese individuals with mild health issues, excluding chronic diseases highlights complex nature of obesity, which influenced by

lifestyle, socioeconomic status, demographic factors and gender differences. Distribution of obesity across different categories of the variables varies. But in most cases no significant association was found, and it could be concluded that certain factors may influence obesity but they do not show a statistically significant impact on obesity.

Statements and Declarations:

Financial interests:

Authors declare that they have no financial interest.

Ethical consideration:

Ethical approval was obtained from the intuitional ethics committee.

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REFERENCES:

1. Sardinha LB, Santos DA, Silva AM, Coelho-e-Silva MJ, Raimundo AM, Moreira H, Santos R, Vale S, Baptista F, Mota J. Prevalence of overweight, obesity, and abdominal obesity in a representative sample of Portuguese adults. *PloS one*. 2012 Oct 31;7(10):e47883.
2. Ayatollahi SM, Ghorehshizadeh Z. Prevalence of obesity and overweight among adults in Iran. *Obesity reviews*. 2010 May;11(5):335-7.
3. Katulanda P, Jayawardena MA, Sheriff MH, Constantine GR, Matthews DR. Prevalence of overweight and obesity in Sri Lankan adults. *Obesity reviews*. 2010 Nov;11(11):751-6.
4. Al-Riyami AA, Afifi MM. Prevalence and correlates of obesity and central obesity among Omani adults. *Saudi medical journal*. 2003 Jun 1;24(6):641-6.
5. Baalwa J, Byarugaba BB, Kabagambe EK, Otim AM. Prevalence of overweight and obesity in young adults in Uganda. *African health sciences*. 2010;10(4).
6. Saha A, Muhammad T, Mandal B, Adhikary M, Barman P. Socio-demographic and behavioral correlates of excess weight and its health consequences among older adults in India: Evidence from a cross-sectional study, 2017–18. *PLoS One*. 2023 Oct 5;18(10):e0291920.
7. Garawi F, Devries K, Thorogood N, Uauy R. Global differences between women and men in the prevalence of obesity: is there an

- association with gender inequality?. *European journal of clinical nutrition*. 2014 Oct;68(10):1101-6.
8. Gupta RD, Tamanna N, Siddika N, Haider SS, Apu EH, Haider MR. Obesity and abdominal obesity in Indian population: findings from a nationally representative study of 698,286 participants. *Epidemiologia*. 2023 May 12;4(2):163-72.
 9. Singh G, Agrawal R, Tripathi N, Verma A. Overweight and obesity, the clock ticking in India? A secondary analysis of trends of prevalence, patterns, and predictors from 2005 to 2020 using the National Family Health Survey. *International Journal of Noncommunicable Diseases*. 2023 Jan 1;8(1):31-45.
 10. Shastri M, Rathod VM, Raval DM, Khan S, Mallik S, Solanki DL. Liver involvement in individuals with obesity: a cross-sectional study from Western India. *The Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*. 2023 Feb 1;71(2):11-2.
 11. Shabu SA. Prevalence of overweight/obesity and associated factors in adults in Erbil, Iraq: A household survey. *Zanco Journal of Medical Sciences (Zanco J Med Sci)*. 2019 Apr 23;23(1):128-34.
 12. Bakir MA, Hammad K, Mohammad L. Prevalence of obesity, central obesity, and associated socio- demographic variables in Syrian women using different anthropometric indicators. *AnthropologicAl review*. 2017 Jun 13;80(2):191-205.
 13. Esmaeily H, Azimi-Nezhad M, Ghayour-Mobarhan M, Parizadeh MR, Safarian M, Parizadeh MJ, Hassankhani B, Salardini E, Houshang ZK, Javad H, Oladi MR. Association between socioeconomic factors and obesity in Iran. *Pak J Nutr*. 2009 Oct 14;8(1):53-6.
 14. Girdhar S, Sharma S, Chaudhary A, Bansal P, Satija M. An epidemiological study of overweight and obesity among women in an urban area of North India. *Indian journal of community medicine*. 2016 Apr 1;41(2):154-7.
 15. Sarma H, Saquib N, Hasan MM, Saquib J, Rahman AS, Khan JR, Uddin MJ, Cullen MR, Ahmed T. Determinants of overweight or obesity among ever-married adult women in Bangladesh. *BMC obesity*. 2016 Dec;3:1-1.
 16. Amegah AK, Lumor S, Vidogo F. Prevalence and determinants of overweight and obesity in adult residents of Cape Coast, Ghana: a hospital-based study. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*. 2011;11(3).
 17. Shri N, Singh S, Singh A. Prevalence and predictors of combined body mass index and waist circumference among Indian adults. *International Journal of Public Health*. 2023 Mar 29;68:1605595.
 18. Yu S, Xing L, Du Z, Tian Y, Jing L, Yan H, Lin M, Zhang B, Liu S, Pan Y, Li C. Prevalence of obesity and associated risk factors and cardiometabolic comorbidities in rural Northeast China. *BioMed research international*. 2019;2019(1):6509083.
 19. Anjana RM, Pradeepa R, Das AK, Deepa M, Bhansali A, Joshi SR, Joshi PP, Dhandhanika VK, Rao PV, Sudha V, Subashini R. Physical activity and inactivity patterns in India—results from the ICMR-INDIAB study (Phase-1)[ICMR-INDIAB-5]. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*. 2014 Dec;11:1-1.
 20. Gartner DR, Taber DR, Hirsch JA, Robinson WR. The spatial distribution of gender differences in obesity prevalence differs from overall obesity prevalence among US adults. *Annals of epidemiology*. 2016 Apr 1;26(4):293-8.